

Rubric for Evaluating an eSports Program for Gifted University Students

Criteria Definitions

- **Improving Cognitive Skills:** This criterion evaluates the development and application of complex cognitive strategies, including problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making abilities.
- **Effective Knowledge Acquisition:** This criterion measures the extent to which students acquire, retain, and apply knowledge in practical contexts.
- **Engagement and Motivation:** This criterion assesses the level of student participation, interest, and commitment to the activities within the eSports program.
- **Development of Digital Competences:** This criterion evaluates proficiency in using digital tools and platforms, essential for navigating and excelling in a technologically driven environment.

Rubric' Objective

The objective of this evaluation rubric is to assess the eSports program's impact on the learning experiences and skill development of GT students. This rubric aims to measure the extent to which the program enhances cognitive skills, facilitates effective knowledge acquisition, boosts engagement and motivation, and develops digital competences. The goal is to ensure that the eSports program supports the holistic development of gifted students, preparing them for complex problem-solving and innovation in academic and real-world contexts.

Rubric Table

Criteria	Level 1 (Basic)	Level 2 (Intermediate)	Level 3 (Advanced)	Weight
Improving Cognitive Skills	0 - 11	12 - 24	25 - 35	35%
	Limited development of cognitive skills, with minimal application of complex strategies.	Moderate development of cognitive skills, applying some complex strategies in specific situations.	Advanced development of cognitive skills, effectively and consistently applying complex strategies in various situations.	
Effective Knowledge Acquisition	0 - 9	10 - 19	20 - 30	30%
	Basic knowledge acquisition with poor retention and application in practical contexts.	Intermediate knowledge acquisition with occasional retention and application in practical contexts.	Advanced knowledge acquisition with high retention and effective, consistent application in various practical contexts.	

Engagement and Motivation	0 - 6	7 - 13	14 - 20	20%
	Limited participation and motivation, with low involvement in program activities.	Moderate participation and motivation, showing interest and commitment in some program activities.	High participation and motivation, with significant involvement and commitment in all program activities.	
Development of Digital Competences	0 - 4	5 - 9	10 - 15	15%
	Limited development of digital competences, with minimal proficiency in using digital tools and platforms.	Moderate development of digital competences, with proficiency in using some digital tools and platforms.	Advanced development of digital competences, with high proficiency in using various digital tools and platforms effectively.	
			Total:	100%

Justification:

In this section, reviewers should specify the rationale for their rating on each criteria.

Highlights:

In this section the reviewers should mention the most significant strengths of the program related to GT education.

Improvement needs:

In this section, reviewers should include comments about areas that can be improved in the program for a better learning experience for the gifted and talent.